

Research Article

Implementing Gamified Systems in Coffeeshop Business to Increase Customer Engagement, Satisfaction, and Loyalty

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Abstract: Coffeeshop business often faced fierce competition with the emergence of new and existing competitors. Customers often have considerable number of choices in deciding coffeeshop to satisfy their coffee needs. Basically, many strategies have been implemented to become the first choice of customer such as the introduction of signature menu, interior design, friendly staff, and strategic location. However, only few investigates the utilization of ICT advancement to capture customer engagement, satisfaction, and loyalty. Due to the advancement of ICT, the customer needs are further complicated thus, coffeeshop business need to utilize the benefits of ICT. As such, this paper explores the implementation of gamified systems such as rewarding system that consists of points, badges, leaderboard, and rankings to enhance customer experience. The implementation of gamified systems in the 1997 coffee shows the way to successfully increase customer experience, hence, it can be commercialized for other coffeeshop to increase their competitiveness through gamified systems.

Keywords: gamified systems; gamification; coffeeshop business.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Gamified systems were used in business to increase customer engagement, satisfaction, and loyalty (Durinik, 2014; Vanick & Bui, 2014). Gamified systems include rewarding systems that frequently reward the customer through points and badges. For instance, every purchase from customer in the coffeeshop would receive points as rewards. These points can be used to claim other rewards such as free cup of coffee, free cakes, and free meals. In term of badges, every order and transactions of customer will be recorded and counted. If the customer has collected significant number of orders, they will receive badge. This badge is systematically categorized ranging from premium to exclusive badges. The more orders customers have, the higher ranks badge they will receive. A higher rank badges resulting in higher discount offers for the next purchase. The implementation of point and badge systems have greatly influence customer engagement, satisfaction, and loyalty (Aljameel, 2020). However, few coffeeshop business have implement these gamified systems into their business. Instead, they are relying on traditional card punctuation for customer to receive free coffee as rewards. The use

of punctuation cards has proved to significantly influence customer retention, however, the cards sometimes can suffer from various issue, such as loss and damage. The implementation of gamified systems by using the advancement of ICT would only require to scan the QR codes and filling up a simple form, thus, they can have their own virtual profile. Moreover, they can edit their virtual profile by filling more important information such as phone numbers, email, date of birth and flavour preferences. This information is stored in centralized database and proved to be valuable for coffeeshop business to offer promotion, marketing, and give surprise and systematic rewards. By having this kind of gamified systems, most likely the customer would feel valued thus increase their retention, engagement, satisfaction, and engagement because of the dopamine effect from the rewarding systems.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Durinik (2014) provides an overview of implementing gamification elements in KMS among employee. Among the gamified elements that we explored are points, badges, challenges and contests, awards and prizes, and ranking and leaderboards. Durinik (2014) explained how these gamified elements have increase employee engagement and satisfaction. This is because the nature of competitiveness in human drives them to accept challenges and contest, in order to achieve higher ranks in ranking and leaderboards. Once they achieved the coveted spot, the dopamine is released in their brain hence influence their satisfaction and engagement towards the system. The study of Durinik (2014) have provide direction for coffeeshop business owner to consider implementing these gamified systems in order to increase their customer engagement towards the coffeeshop systems, hence increasing their satisfaction and loyalty. This enable the coffeeshop to gain competitive advantage towards other coffeeshop that did not employ these gamified elements.

Warnick & Bui (2014) provide systematic analysis of 203 papers that address gamification applications in various fields that includes finance, risk management, human resource management, and corporate governance. This study has provided a framework towards implementing gamification system in the management areas to increase employee engagement, work rate, commitment, and satisfaction. Moreover, the study has pinpointed a future direction towards investigating the impacts of gamification systems towards employee work excellence. This paper focusing on gamification design elements and strategy by top management to alleviate their employee competitiveness to receive recognition and rewards, hence, increasing the productivity of both employee and organization. The study of Warnick & Bui (2014) highlighted the importance of designing and strategizing the gamification systems that includes the reward structure and challenges level. In the context of coffeeshop business, the study of Warnick & Bui (2014) can be used as basis to design the gamified systems in terms of how to structure the point and redeem systems, the requirement to achieve badge and how to design the badges level for the rewards system.

Hamari et al., (2014) provide reviews on empirical studies on gamification and develop a framework to evaluate the effects of gamification towards behavioral outcomes. The finding of the study revealed that gamification significantly influenced positive behavioral outcomes, however, the authors stated that despite the clear benefits of gamification, there is lack of research examining the outcome of behavior in related to gamification systems. It is important to note that, the authors highlighted the positive effects of behavior however is related to the how gamification systems were implemented as well as the kind of user using it. This study postulated that the gamification systems need to be carefully designed and the designer must take into consideration the kind of user that will use the system. This study further supports the findings of Warnick & Bui (2014) that emphasized on the design elements and strategies in implementing gamified systems. Thus, for coffee business owners, it is important to study and review the framework proposed by Warnick & Bui (2014) in designing the gamification elements, in order to maximize the benefits of gamification systems implementations.

In relation to the gamification framework, the study of Kappen & Nacke (2013) further highlights the strategy and creative design techniques of gamified systems in business applications. The authors highlighted that the creator of the gamification systems faced challenge in strategizing and creating the structure of gamified elements in a playful way to maximize the engagement, satisfaction, and loyalty. Kappen & Nacke (2013) explains there are limited framework and model for business application to effectively implement gamified systems to increase customer engagement, satisfaction, and loyalty. The authors suggest that creator of gamified systems to delve into self-determination theory and the principles of system design to inculcate the gamification systems on business application. Hence, the authors provide the design guideline to maximize the effects. From this study, coffee business owners are able to refer to this guideline and framework to ensure maximize effect of the gamified systems. This is because, in order to implement gamified systems, a significant amount of money need to be spent on the rewards, system development, discounts, and other exclusive benefits.

3. METHODS

By considering the frameworks of Warnick & Bui (2014) and Hamari et al., (2014), as well as the guideline provided by Kappen & Nacke (2013), this study implements the gamified systems towards coffee shop business named The 1997 Coffee, which is located at Sungai Petani, Kedah, North Malaysia. The website of The 1997 Coffee was designed and gamified systems point and badges were implemented in the website. For points, each Ringgit Malaysia (RM) purchase resulted 1 point for customer. For instance, if the customer buys the coffee that the price is RM 10, then 10 points will be allocated to the customer account. Then, the points are redeemable started at 30 points, 50 points, 70 points, and 100 points. The higher the points, the more exclusive the rewards. The rewards for points redemption includes free cup of coffee, free layer of cakes, and free meals. For badges, customers are able to view their progress via the order. Once a customer made order, they will receive 1 progression point to acquire badges. The badges are categorized into three, namely, silver badge customer, premium customer, and exclusive customer. In order to achieve silver badge, customer need to have 10 progression points via order, while to receive the premium customer badge, they need 30 progression points. Lastly, in order to received the coveted exclusive badge, they would need 50 progression points. The silver badge enable customer to enjoy 5% of discount for every next purchase, while the customers with premium badges are entitled to 10% of discount, whereas the exclusive member enjoys 15% discount for every purchase. These gamified systems were designed in accordance with the frameworks proposed by Warnick & Bui (2014) and Hamari et al., (2014), as well as following the guideline proposed by Kappen & Nacke (2013).

4. FINDINGS

Customer would be able to purchase even without registering to the system, this is to give the autonomy for the customer. Autonomy is proved to significantly affect customer behavior in which majority of customer dislikes if they have limited options or empowerment. This is the gamification guideline as proposed by Kappen & Nacke (2013) as the gamification elements would allow autonomy and empowerment for clients to feel in control to made decisions. However, the employee would politely suggest to the customer if they register by completing minimal form, they would be able to receive points, badges, and gifts. The employee plays a crucial role towards persuading customer to register. Figure 1 shows the registration form for the customer.

After registration, customer would be able to view their profile in the system. In their profile page, there are two tabs, namely profile and badges & progress. In the profile page, customer would be able to see clearly their current points. The points will be given in accordance to their purchase, for

instance, every RM1 spent the customer would receive 1 point. Below the points, the customer is greeted with their given name, and their personal information such as email, address, profile picture, phone number, date of birth, and favorite drinks. In this personal information section, the customer is given the options to edit their information at any time. Other than that, their purchase history, points earned, and current point are displayed along with the recent transactions. By providing this information, the customer would feel satisfied as every purchased is seen as being valued by the coffee shop (Wunderlich et al., 2019). In the badges & progress tab, customer would be able to monitor their progress towards achieving the coveted badges. By providing the real time feedback monitoring, this would increase the eagerness of the customer to engage more with the system, in order to unlock the coveted badges (Herzig et al., 2015). Figure 2 and Figure 3 depicts the customer profile and badges & progress tab respectively.

Figure 1. Registration Form

Figure 2. Customer Profile

Figure 3. Badges & Progress

Customer are allowed to browse the menu available via coffeeshop website by scanning the QR code. After the customer made their choice, they can just click add to cart whatever drinks and meals that they preferred. After confirming the transaction, customer would see the points being allocated to their profile. Figure 4 shows how the system allocate points to the customer. After having significant number of points, customer able to view the redeem tab in the website to see what they can redeem from the points they gained. If they decide to redeem the items, their point will be deducted based on the points required to redeem the items. This technique is proven to influence customer satisfaction and engagement. Figure 5 depicts the redeem tab for customer.

Figure 4. Points Allocation

Figure 5. Redeem Points

5. DISCUSSION

The effort to implement gamified system in coffeeshop business is to increase customer engagement, satisfaction, and loyalty (Aljameel, 2020; Hamari et al., 2014; Wanick & Bui, 2014) given the fierce competition coffeeshop are entitled to. The gamification system work wonders due to the release of dopamine in the brain of customer when they receive certain rewards (Pacewicz, 2015). When the dopamine is released, customer would feel satisfied, thrilled, enjoyed, and mesmerized thus most likely to repeat the purchase and engage more with the system. Coffee business nowadays should include gamification systems in their business to increase their competitiveness and give them edge over their competitors by providing gifts and rewards to their customer via gamification systems. The implementation of gamification systems however, need considerable strategies and techniques to maximized benefits. In order to successfully implement gamification systems, coffeeshop owners are advised to follow the frameworks and guidelines that have been provided by researchers, academicians, and scholars (Kappen & Nacke, 2013; Wanick & Bui, 2014; Hamari et al., 2014).

Dopamine is the chemical in human brain that is released upon triggers (Pacewicz, 2015) Dopamine has the effect to made human feel addicted, this is why the gaming industry generated billions of dollars per year (The Forbes, 2023). They instil the well-structured gamified systems such as the challenges and events, the point and badge systems, as well as leaderboard and ranking systems. Their user would feel enjoyment, excitement, and exhilarating once they received points, achieve badges, earning coveted ranking in the leaderboards because the dopamine has been greatly released by their brains (Pacewicz, 2015). This dopamine would make them addicted to the game, hence increase their engagement, thus triggers them to made purchase the in-game virtual assets such as coins, weapons, players, and others to give them competitive advantage over their rivals (Wunderlich et al., 2019). This dopamine effect has been greatly studied and been instil in other context, such as coffeeshop business.

6. CONCLUSION

Gamified systems need to be implemented not only in coffeeshop business, but in other domains such as barbershop, car & motorcycle workshop, saloon & beauty, groceries shop, shopping complex, and hardware shops. This is because the gamified systems have been proven to significantly increase the customer engagement, satisfaction, and loyalty. The gamification systems are capable to trigger the dopamine release in the human brains, enhancing their overall experience and feel attached emotionally towards the product or brand. Gamified system also should be implemented in other domain such as academics, banking, architecture, aviation, and medical to further advance the areas.

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